

Rethinking Composite Indicators: A Geographical Perspective

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Summary

This paper critiques traditional composite indicators, arguing that their fixed weighting schemes oversimplify complex geographical realities. Using the English Index of Multiple Deprivation, it highlights how static indicators mask local variations. The study explores spatially adaptive methods, particularly Benefit-of-Doubt (BoD) analysis, which allows regions to assign optimal weights to deprivation factors. BoD-derived indicators reveal hidden spatial patterns and offer a more nuanced understanding of inequalities. Through mapping and analysis, the study demonstrates that these methods provide more context-aware insights, helping policymakers design targeted interventions rather than relying on rigid, one-size-fits-all indices.

KEYWORDS: Composite Indicators, Spatial Analysis, Benefit-of-Doubt, Deprivation Indices, GIS

1 Introduction

Composite indicators where a number of variables related to a particular topic are combined into a weighted sum, are widely used across various domains from policy evaluation to economic assessments and quality-of-life studies. However, conventional indicators often suffer from significant limitations. Aggregating multiple dimensions into a single score frequently leads to an oversimplification of complex realities. This approach can mask local disparities, misrepresent true performance, and inadvertently encourage competitive and inappropriate ranking rather than a genuine understanding of spatial and contextual variations.

This paper proposes a focus on more nuanced, spatially aware alternatives. An example using the *English Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD)* is used to demonstrate how deprivation indicators — a kind of composite indicator — can mask patterns occurring across several variables. One issue is that variable weighting contributing to the construction of indices is fixed across all geographical units, whereas relative importance may be spatially heterogenous. An example of a method using

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spatially varying weighting methods, *Benefit-of-Doubt (BoD) analysis* (Cherchye et al., 2007; Rogge, 2018) is an alternative to geographically static weights. It will be shown that composite indicators of this kind allow different aspects of the data to be mapped, and that spatial patterns in the data can be usefully unpacked in novel and insightful ways.

2 The Limitations of Traditional Performance Indicators

Performance indicators are typically constructed as weighted combinations of multiple variables, producing composite indices for comparison and ranking. Examples include university league tables, deprivation indices, and economic performance rankings.

While such indicators are sometimes convenient for broad comparisons, and are easily understood provided their limitations are appreciated, they often fail to capture complex underlying conditions. Problems include:

- **A one-size-fits-all approach:** These indicators assume that the same factors contribute equally across all regions.
- **Encouragement of ‘League Tables’ :** Indicators tend to encourage rankings, which obscure multidimensional differences and promote competition over meaningful insight.
- **Lack of geographical adaptability:** Geographically fixed weights do not allow for local contexts and conditions.

Using the *Living Environment Deprivation Domain* from the *English Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD)* (Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government, 2019), these problems may be illustrated. The idea of the IMD is to provide a composite indicator of deprivation - higher values are intended to signify greater levels of deprivation. A geographically constant set of weights for these variables does not reflect local concerns. For instance, in an urban setting, air pollution might be the dominant concern, whereas, in rural areas, poor quality housing may be a greater issue. Applying the same weighting across all regions is an oversimplification that could lead to inappropriately geographical targeting of policy interventions.

3 Geographical Approaches to Composite Indicators

To help to counter these issues, spatially varying weighting approaches may be adopted. These allow different weights to be used for different places to emphasize different contributors to deprivation. Such approaches include:

- **Benefit-of-Doubt (BoD) analysis:** This method allows each location to determine the optimal weighting of different indicators to best represent its own deprivation level.
- **Order Weighted Averaging (OWA):** Unlike traditional weighted averaging, the weights do not correspond directly to specific criteria but rather to their ranking after sorting across the scaled variables for each spatial unit (Yager, 1988). This approach integrates geographical context into the weighting process to adjust indicator influence based on spatial location. Although this itself allows weights to vary geographically, as the ranks of variables change from place to place, further geographical weighting can also be applied (Fusco et al., 2024).

- **Geographically Weighted Principal Component Analysis** (Harris et al., 2011) - Principal components is used to assign weights, but on a geographically weighted basis.

Each of these offer different kinds of insight, and it is intended to consider all of them as potential approaches. However, in this study, the focus will be on Benefit-of-Doubt analysis.

3.1 Benefit of Doubt (BoD) Analysis

Using BoD analysis, each local area to “bids” for a high composite deprivation score by choosing its own weights for the individual variables, placing emphasis on the specific variables that contribute to deprivation. Without constraint, this process would lead to uncontrolled increases in indices, and so some form of benchmarking is needed. Thus, once a set of weights is proposed, it is applied to *all* places in the region under study. The place scoring the highest with these rates is scaled at 100 (the benchmark) and the place choosing the weights is scaled in proportion to this. Thus, the place choosing the weights will score less than 100, unless it actually has the highest deprivation score for these weights.

As a final adjustment - it is worth noting that if a place were assigned an unwise set of weights it may lose out, as a better set, giving a higher score may exist. However, it is possible (using linear programming) to compute the *optimal* set of weights for each place and to use these. Thus, once this process is complete, each place will have, as attributes, a set of weights and an overall composite indicator. Mapping the both the composite scores and each of the weights allows both the extent *and* the nature of the deprivation to be visualised.

The optimisation process is outlined more precisely as follows: Assume there are N areas and k individual indicators. Let x_{ij} denote the observed value of indicator i ($i = 1, \dots, k$) for area j ($j = 1, \dots, N$). We focus on a specific area, say area A , with indicator levels x_{iA} . The objective is to choose nonnegative weights w_1, w_2, \dots, w_k that maximize area A 's composite score, subject to constraints ensuring that no areas's weighted sum exceeds 100.

Then the BoD linear program model can be written as in Equation 1.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{BoD} &= \max_{w_i} \left[\sum_{i=1}^k w_i x_{iA} \right] \\ \text{subject to} \quad & \sum_{i=1}^k w_i x_{ij} \leq 100, \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, N, \\ \text{and} \quad & w_i \geq 0, \quad \forall i. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The linear programming problem in Equation 1 is solved in turn for areas $A = 1, \dots, N$. The maximum value for $\sum_{i=1}^k w_i x_{iA}$ found is the score for area A . Of course, these scores may be ranked, but this alone does not tell a full story. More insight can be gained by considering spatial patterns in the emphasis on the weights applied to the variables for each area.

4 Mapping Spatial Inequalities with BoD Analysis

Here, the idea is demonstrated using the Living Environment Deprivation Domain (Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government, 2019). This is a composite index using four variables

- subdivided into ‘indoors’ and ‘outdoors’ sub-domains - Table 1.

Table 1: Living Environment Deprivation variables

Sub-Domain	Description	Name
Indoors	Houses without central heating	No_heating
	Housing in poor condition (failing to meet the Decent Homes standard)	Housing_poor
Outdoors	Air quality (based on emissions rates for four pollutants)	AQ
	Road traffic accidents involving injury to pedestrians and cyclists	RTA_rate

Here, each of these sub-indicators are scaled to range from 0 to 1, and are mapped in Figure 1. Note that in the case where weights for each variable are fixed for all areas, these maps correspond to the individual components of a conventional composite indicator. The spatial units used are Lower Super Output Areas (LSOAs).

Figure 1: The variables in the Quality of Living index.

Each of these has notably different patterns - for example the pattern of the north circular road is quite visible on the air quality map - as is the area close to Heathrow Airport. Also, a cluster of areas of poor housing exists just south of the River Thames (Clapham, Balham for example), not apparent on the other maps.

The Benefit of Doubt index was computed using these variables. The result is shown in Figure 2, shown next to the standard Living Environment Score used as part of the Index of Multiple Deprivation. It is notable that the BoD map has generally higher index values - this is unsurprising, due to the optimising nature of the algorithm used to create it. However, also of note is the way that certain aspects of quality of living are highlighted in certain areas in the BoD map, that do not show in the standard map. For example the air quality issues near to Heathrow Airport. Similarly an area near to Barking appears in the BoD map. These differences are apparent when considering the composite index itself, but as argued above, different places have different living quality issues, and a much greater understanding by considering the nature of these issues, and their individual geographies.

Figure 2: Comparison of Quality of Living Scores

Looking at the geographical distributions of the weights reveal the dominant deprivation factors in different regions (Figure 3). One very notable difference is that air quality as a factor in this index has a very different geography to the other variables - focusing more near the central regions of London.

Figure 3: The Benefit-of-Doubt Quality of Living index weights.

However, this shows the geography of key variables, but not the level. A final set of maps shows the variable *multiplied by* the weight for each variable. This not only shows which variables are important, but how much each one contributes to the overall BoD score (Figure 4).

Figure 4: The Benefit-of-Doubt Quality of Living index contributions.

These maps provide a more effective tool for policymakers, helping to ensure that interventions are targeted according to the actual needs of specific areas. Rather than enforcing a uniform weighting scheme, BoD analysis allows for the development of regionally adapted policies that align with local realities.

5 Conclusion

Indicators of one dimension are useful tools for representing more nuanced multidimensional patterns in a single map or chart. However, representing this information should not necessarily suggest a ranking process - the method here highlights areas where *some kind* of issue occurs, but this then provides a focus for investigating the *nature* of the issue through maps such as those in Figure 3 and Figure 4. Further development of these ideas could include identifying particular patterns in the weights or contributions in the specific areas, possibly using cluster analysis - to explore whether there are specific 'patterns of need' which may relate to particular regions showing particular kinds of need. Combined with a general benefit of doubt indicator this could be a useful exploratory

tool. Other possible amendments could also be applied, such as limiting the overall contribution any given weight could have - thus creating a hybrid index, stopping the index being dominated by a single variable. This could be achieved by adding further constraints to the linear program specification.

Finally, there is a likely need to explain the working of this index to a broader audience of potential end users. Although the concept of the index is relatively easy to explain, there is currently little material to disseminate the idea amongst the GI user community, or quantitative policy analysts. Explanatory material including use cases would be an important contribution here.

Biography

Prof. Chris Brunsdon is a Professor of Geocomputation at Maynooth University and a leading researcher in spatial statistics and geographical data science. His main research interests include the development and application of statistical and computational methods for spatial and spatio-temporal data analysis. He has contributed extensively to the field of Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) and its extensions. He has co-authored several influential books including ‘An Introduction to R for Spatial Analysis and Mapping’ with Lex Comber. Chris is currently involved in research projects involving the applications of these methods to health data.

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